

**ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT OF HANDICRAFT SECTOR BY VARIOUS
SCHEMES IN JAMMU AND KASHMIR.**

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Abstract:

After agriculture, the handicraft sector is India's second largest unorganized and employment-generating sector. In ancient times or in the past, it was a good source of foreign exchange. This research paper aims to look into the level of handicraft schemes among Jammu and Kashmir's entrepreneurs. Most of the schemes are overseen by the Ministry of Textile, but many entrepreneurs face financial challenges, as well as a lack of technical expertise, awareness of government programmes, and market knowledge. The researcher looked at a variety of journals, reports, and websites, among other things. In the State of Jammu and Kashmir various avenues of business are available like Tourism, Agriculture, Export business, Handicrafts etc. Jammu and Kashmir handicrafts production and distribution offers great market potential for aspiring Entrepreneurs due to the high demand for products and high local economic returns. Furthermore, Jammu and Kashmir handicrafts have proven to be highly lucrative products in local, domestic and international markets. However, the sector is in great need of passionate, determined youth entrepreneurs to take Jammu and Kashmir handicrafts to new heights. Jammu and Kashmir handicrafts are rare treasures due to their aesthetically pleasing, often handmade craftsmanship. Also, they are sourced from organic raw materials such as cotton, silk, wool and wood making them even more unique in the international market. The traditional embroidered designs are exquisite and intricate, having been passed down through the generations maintaining such beauty which often reflects Jammu and Kashmir's natural landscape and rich cultural history.

Keywords: Handicraft, Entrepreneurship, Schemes, Development, Employment.

Introduction:

The economy of Jammu and Kashmir is agrarian in nature, similar to the national economy, but unlike the national economy, the state's economy is characterized by a lack of a significant industrial sector. The state's economy, on the other hand, is still doing well thanks to the handicrafts sector's major contribution.

On the basis of various aspects of its beauty, the state of Jammu and Kashmir is regarded as the "paradise on earth." Its artistic nature, which is largely expressed in the art and beauty of its handicraft goods, adds to its beauty. The state of Jammu and Kashmir is aptly dubbed the "beauty bowl of India" due to the artistic beauty of its handicraft products. The state of Jammu and Kashmir has a fascinating and long history of handicrafts. Handicrafts were brought to the state of Jammu and Kashmir during the reign of Zain-UI-Abidin. Zain-UI-Abidin, also known as Bud Shah, recruited professional craftsmen from Central Asia to train local residents in a variety of handicrafts that were previously unknown to the state's residents. This expertise was passed down from

generation to generation thanks to royal patronage and encouragement from various kings, princesses, and tourists, as well as the government.

The economy of Jammu and Kashmir, like that of all emerging economies, is characterized by the coexistence of traditional and modern industrial sectors. However, the modern industrial sector in Jammu and Kashmir is restricted in its growth, owing to the absence of a broad industrial sector. This has resulted in a situation in which the state's economy must rely heavily on conventional industries for growth and development. This implies that traditional industries, especially handicrafts, continue to be the state's economic backbone. Handicrafts and handloom are labor intensive in nature. They provide gainful employment to a vast section of the population in the state. By providing gainful employment to about 4.10 lakh people, they have become a means to reduce poverty in the state (Economic Survey, 2016). The words of Tiruvalluva, the sage-poet, when he wrote that “nothing is more dreadful and painful than poverty” and “gripping poverty robs a man of the lofty nobility of his descent” are true today as they were when written more than two thousand years ago. These wise-words poet's testify to the fact that handicrafts play an important role in alleviating poverty by providing a source of income for the state's poor. Handicrafts businesses are especially important for the poor and backward sections of the population. The government, through its policymaking, must concentrate on providing this sector with the requisite support in terms of financial resources, ability and skills upgrades, and appropriate technology.

11 Handicraft Products of Jammu and Kashmir:

Shawls: The finest shawl to the world is given by Kashmir. Kashmiri shawls are made from three fibers they are wool, Pashmina and Shahtoosh and decorated by Sozni, Motifs embroidery types. Pashmina, yarn is spun got from the hair of the ibex though pure pashmina is expensive, but semi or mixed Pashmina is affordable. Shahtoosh, the legendary ‘ring shawl’ is famous for its lightness, softness and warmth but it is a banned item now.

Papier Mache: These products are made of the pulp of paper and adhesive. To make a product of Papier Mache, paper is soaked in water till it disintegrates. It is then pounded, mixed with an adhesive solution, shaped over moulds, and allowed to dry and set before being painted and varnished. There is a big variety in artistry and the choices of the colors. Prices are decided by the material used to decorate this artwork.

Silverware: It is one of the ancient arts in Kashmir, Kashmiri silverware, especially ornamental picture-frames, is in great demand in the markets of United States, European countries and Australia. The work known as ‘Naqash’ determines the price of the object, as does the weight.

Wood Carving: wood-carving is one of the best known cottage industries of the valley Kashmiri walnut and Chinar wood has a fine texture and smooth grain patterns, making the wood expensive. The price of the wooden piece of craft depends on the grain pattern of the wood used, the detailing of the carving and the part of the tree used.

Basketry: Willow rushes that grow in plenty in the marshes and lakes of Kashmir are used to make some beautiful objects, ranging from shopping baskets and lampshades to tables and chairs, all in affordable ranges.

Phool Kari - A traditional craft, recently revived, is Phoolkari, Bagh or Shaloo embroidered in the phoolkari style was an essential part of the bride's trousers till only a few decades

back. A craft with its origin in Punjab Phoolkari, as the very name suggests is a style of embroidery of floral designs. The present day designs, however, are by no means limited to flowers alone and include a variety of other patterns.

Bassoli Paintings: Basali is a town located in the foot-hills of Shivalik Mountains in Kathua District of Jammu Division. In the late 17th century, Basali emerged as a great centre of painting. According to well known Dr. Herman Goltz, "Basali painting are among the great achievements of Indians". Their central inspiration is vashnavism; the themes have been taken from the epics and the puranas. The different themes of the paintings are religious (Gita Govinda and Ramayana), secular, historical, contemporary and literary. Besides the paintings bring out extreme emotion combined with a lyrical sense of Basali landscape.

Calico Painting: Samba, a small town about 40 kms from Jammu, on Jammu Pathankot highway is a well known centre of Block Printing. Calico Printing enjoys a wide popularity. Printing in vegetable color with help of wooden blocks on hand woven cotton cloth is being used as cool, comfortable, floor/bed coverings and are in great demand.

Thangka Paintings: Thangkas are religious painted scrolls depicting Buddhist deities, traditionally done on cloth. Over the years, techniques like embroidery and applique have been added. They are believed to be pictures of the spiritual worlds. Thangka is a traditional form of Buddhist art with Tibetan, Indian, Chinese, and Nepalese influences. Hence there are different schools and styles. Various factors determine this - geography, availability of raw materials, socio-cultural influences and the schools of Buddhism they follow. This Painting is found in the ladakh division of Jammu and Kashmir.

1.12 Importance of Handicraft Sector:

Handicrafts are important for both cultural and economic reasons. Heritage conservation, skill creation, and art development are all guided by the cultural importance of handicrafts. Although its economic status is based on job growth, low capital use, high value addition, and export/foreign exchange earnings potential. The handicrafts industry is India's largest fragmented and unorganized sector, as well as the state economy (Vijayagopalan, 1993), and one of the country's largest foreign exchange earners. Since the dawn of civilization, state and Indian craftsmanship has been a way of life. When Europeans found a sea route to colonies, this trade became globalised. Even before Vasco de Gama discovered a sea route to India in 1498 A.D., this trade gained worldwide attention. Local crafts were transported by artisans who travelled all over the world with the aid of forward-thinking merchants.

Review of Literature:

Gowda and Shetty, (2010), have provided some significant suggestions for strengthening the MSMEs in India. They are a continuation of incentive packages to MSMEs, procurement policy by the public sector to be introduced at the earliest and setting up an autonomous body at the central level for the development and promotion of MSMEs.

Karthihaiselvi, Neelamegam, and Magesan, (2010), In India, the importance of SSI has been investigated. Over the last ten years, the share of Small Scale Industries exports has increased in most sectors, according to the report. They also recognize that India has a

wealth of natural resources. Now is the time for the government to step in and help existing and aspiring entrepreneurs by providing loan facilities and appropriate training.

The report presented by **Ministry of Textiles (2005-06)** stated that the pace and development of different states of the country in handicraft sector has been uneven. Some states, such as Jammu and Kashmir, have made significant progress, while others have lagged behind. According to the study, there are a lot of job opportunities in this sector. According to the study, industrial projects must be an integral part of the overall development plan in order to make the greatest contribution to raising people's income and living standards.

Lone, A. T., and Dar, H. K. (2012), analyzed credit funding and business prospects for Kashmir valley carpet owners. This research used a sample of 30 owners from two blocks in the Kulgam district: Kulgam and D. H. Pora. 15 of the 30 owners were pure owners, while the other 15 were owner weavers, who served as both weavers and owners. For the selection of these units, a purposive sampling technique was used, and SPSS version 20.0 was used for data processing. The findings of the study revealed that while 70% of the owners had obtained loans from formal financial institutions, 30% had not, and the majority of those who had not received a loan from the formal system cited the banks' demand for guarantor and protection as a major reason. According to the findings of the survey, only 30% of owners directly market their goods, while the majority of owners, 70%, do not sell carpet products themselves and instead sell them to middlemen, with the remaining 35% selling to the final seller.

Dr. R Sarvamangala, (2012), revealed that small-scale businesses had a minor issue with selling their goods. Problems arise as a result of factors such as product inconsistency, small scale production, competition from technically more efficient units, lack of market knowledge, low demand, and so on. In addition to the lack of sufficient marketing facilities, the cost of promoting and selling their goods is often too high.

Scope of the Study:

Challenging unemployment scenario of Jammu and Kashmir has been exacerbated by long. Tenuous local economy has left many Kashmir's with few or no options for economic engagement. While unemployment impacts all sections of Jammu and Kashmir including handicraft. Eradicating unemployment in J&K is one of the toughest challenges for Indian government. This study is completely focused on the entrepreneurship development in handicraft sector in J&K. Only few studies have being addressed to construct the handicraft entrepreneurship development and its impact on state economic and human development. The concept of Handicraft entrepreneurship development has remained almost unexplored in Jammu and Kashmir and at a larger scale in India as a whole. Hence, there is a need to the researcher to form a view to assess the role and impact of infrastructure development and important schemes as a whole in handicraft entrepreneurship development in selected districts of the selected division of the state of Jammu and Kashmir.

Research Objectives:

To assess the impact of entrepreneurship development in handicraft sector in J&K, below listed objectives have being framed

- To analyze entrepreneurship development of handicraft sector by various schemes in Jammu and Kashmir.
- To present observations, conclusion and make appropriate suggestions for improving the performance of handicraft industry in Jammu and Kashmir.

Research Methodology:

The present research paper is based on both descriptive as well as exploratory in nature and population of the study was all the handicraft entrepreneurs of Jammu and Kashmir. Purposive sampling method was used for data collection and both primary and secondary data were used for the study. Research technique, quantitative has been found to be relevant for the study. 377 data points have been gathered from the respondents on assessing the impact of entrepreneurship development in handicraft sector in J&K. Data has been collected through personal interview. Total respondents contacted for filling questionnaire were 425, out of which 377 respondents have filled the questionnaire completely. Data analysis has been done through the statistical methods like ANOVA, mean, median mode and standard deviation. Entire analysis has been done on SPSS 25.0 version. Likert scale has been used to design the test hypothesis based on the objectives.

Entrepreneurship development of handicraft sector by various schemes in Jammu and Kashmir.

Null Hypothesis: H₀: Government schemes and the involvement of agencies have no significant impact in the development of Handicraft Sector in J&K.

To find the impact of government schemes and the involvement of agencies in promoting entrepreneurship development of handicraft sector by various schemes in Jammu and Kashmir one way ANOVA has been done. As per the results, significant impact has been seen at 95% confidence level on the factors like organizing product specific show (p-value 0.026, ≤ 0.05), creating brand image through promotions (p-value 0.034, ≤ 0.05), organizing live demonstration of the craft (p-value 0.007, ≤ 0.05), creating awareness and marketing for new products (p-value 0.049, ≤ 0.05) and involvement of agencies (p-value 0.045, ≤ 0.05).

Table 4.8

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Help in organizing Indian Handicrafts & Gifts Fair twice a year besides product-specific shows	Between Groups	1.049	1	1.049	1.292	.026
	Within Groups	304.389	375	.812		
	Total	305.438	376			
Create brand image promotion of J&K	Between Groups	.043	1	.043	.044	.034
	Within Groups	366.615	375	.978		

handicrafts abroad through seminars and publicity as well as awareness programs.	Total	366.658	376			
Thematic display and live demonstration of crafts by Master Craftsperson's in exhibitions abroad	Between Groups	.111	1	.111	.158	.007
	Within Groups	262.950	375	.701		
	Total	263.061	376			
Display of new design through exporters for creating awareness and marketing	Between Groups	.332	1	.332	.479	.049
	Within Groups	260.394	375	.694		
	Total	260.727	376			
Involvement of Agencies in the development of Handicraft Sector in J&K	Between Groups	.295	1	.295	.559	.045
	Within Groups	197.806	375	.527		
	Total	198.101	376			

Conclusion: According to the above table following results are as follows:-

- The confidence interval for the difference between the groups and within the groups of different factors are as follows organizing product specific show (1.049, 0.812), creating brand image through promotions (0.043, 0.978), organizing live demonstration of the craft (0.111, 0.701), creating awareness and marketing for new products (0.332, 0.694) and involvement of agencies (0.295, 0.527).
- Degree of freedom for all the parameters between the groups is 1 and within the groups is 375.
- F Statistics for all the factors are as follows organizing product specific show (1.292), creating brand image through promotions (0.044), organizing live demonstration of the craft (0.158), creating awareness and marketing for new products (0.479) and involvement of agencies (0.559).

Hence at 95% confidence level, it is indicated that as per respondents of the selected cities of Jammu and Kashmir Government schemes and the involvement of agencies have significant impact in the development of Handicraft Sector in J&K. Hence H_1^5 is accepted.

Findings:

Finding of the study is based on the analysis done on SPSS 25.0 version software. As per the overall results entrepreneurship development in handicraft sector in Jammu & Kashmir state is found to be significant. Study reveals that entrepreneurship development especially in handicraft sector is no doubt is the upcoming future of the country. Handicraft sector has its own agility with no limit. This sector (handicraft) is the most dynamic and resourceful segment of rural economy especially in J&K. Now a day through MSME government is trying to support entrepreneurship especially in handicraft sector. This sector is on the highest priority list in the government records and books as per (Anindya Mitra, Sujit Kumar Paul,

2017). Hence, in order to support environment promotion or working on handicraft industry has become countries requirement.

- 85.4% respondents agreed on the involvement of agencies in the development of handicraft sector in J&K.
- Involvement of Agencies in the development of Handicraft Sector in J&K has shown a significant impact on indentify customer in handicraft sector ($p\text{-value}\leq 0.000$), average monthly income ($p\text{-value}\leq 0.000$) and occupation ($p\text{-value}\leq 0.033$).
- Policies, programs, institutional networks and the involvement of agencies have an impact in the development of handicraft sector in J&K.

Conclusion:

Significant impact of schemes and the involvement of agencies in the development of handicraft sector in J&K. as per (Showkat, Sharad Tiwari, 2014) skill training and development programs have positive impact on the production, economic growth and employment generation. Hence, in the last it can be concluded that handicraft sector is one of the largest employment provider in the world and to support this sector, development of entrepreneurship is the necessity. These entrepreneurs with their strong desire can bring the business to the country and the artisans. From this work these artisans will be economically gainful which eventually bring value addition to their social life and family. This process will also help handicraft sector to lead promotion for sustainable growth and livelihood. Overall due to this handicraft sector will get more significant strength for their existence.

Recommendations:

Results of the study provide insights related development of the entrepreneurs in handicraft sector in J&K. This study will also be helpful to the entrepreneurs to know the problems faced by handcraft artisans. Hence, listed below are few recommendations from the study on entrepreneurship development in the handicraft sector in Jammu & Kashmir:-

- Significant improvement is recommended in the process of the development of SMEs.
- Government needs to work more closely with the entrepreneurs and help them in increasing handicraft sector in J&K.
- Capital availability should be foster by the banks in low interest rate

References:

- ❖ Annual Report by Ministry of Textiles: Government of India. (2005-06).
- ❖ (2016) Statistics, Economic survey 2015-2016. Economics and statistics. Jammu and Kashmir government.
- ❖ Bhat, F. A. and Yasmin, E. (2013). An Evaluation of Handicraft Sector of J&K: A Case study of District Budgam. European Academic Journal. Vol. 1. p. 367-381.
- ❖ Ghose, S. M. (2012). Indian Handicrafts Industry: Problems and Strategies.
- ❖ Naik, S. G., & Jayadatta, S. (2020). FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS AND ITS ROLE IN DEVELOPING MSME'S IN INDIA IN PRESENT CONTEXT. Editorial Board, 9(4), 58.
- ❖ Karthihaiselvi, V., Neelamegam, R. and Magesan, A. A. (2010), "Significance of small scale industries in India". Southern Economist, Vol.49 (10)

- ❖ Shah, M. R. (2016, May 2). An Assessment of Handicraft Sector of J&K with Reference to Central Kashmir. School of Commerce, DAVV Indore .
- ❖ Showkat, Sharad Tiwari. (2014). Skill Development and Vocational Training in the Handicraft Sector in Jammu and Kashmir. Annual Research Journal of Symbiosis Centre for Management Studies .